

Engineer or Math Teacher? – Career Preferences among Double-Degree Students in Engineering and Education

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Abstract

The shortage of STEM teachers in Europe poses a significant challenge. To address this issue in Sweden, Chalmers University of Technology offers a double-degree program in engineering and education. This study examines why students choose a double degree in engineering and education, and how internal and external factors influence their eventual career choice. Using semi-structured interviews with thirteen students nearing the completion of their studies, we explore their reasons for enrolling in the program and their perspectives on working as either engineers or teachers. Participants were asked to reflect on key individuals or experiences that shaped their views on these career paths. Key themes include intrinsic motivation, e.g., desire to help others, societal contribution, the impact of school practicum experiences, and the tension between perceived prestige of engineering and the meaningfulness of teaching. The teaching practicum in schools had a significant influence on career decisions. Some students found it deeply meaningful, reinforcing their commitment to education. Financial considerations had little impact, while job security and perceived societal respect were more decisive factors. Several students noted that engineering is generally regarded as the more prestigious career, leading them to frequently justify their choice of teaching to friends and family.

Introduction

Europe faces a persistent shortage of qualified STEM teachers, threatening efforts to sustain technological innovation and student engagement in science. (European Commission, 2023). Teachers are pivotal in inspiring future generations to pursue science and engineering careers, yet engineering graduates seldom consider teaching as a primary professional path.

In response to this challenge, Chalmers University of Technology in 2011 introduced a double-degree program in engineering and education, enabling students to qualify both as engineers and as upper secondary school teachers in mathematics and science (Bengmark, Lundh & Gerlee, 2021).

Students enter the double-degree pathway by enrolling in the master's program Learning and Leadership after completing a bachelor's in engineering at Chalmers. This master's program attracts about 20 students annually, i.e. about 1% of the cohort at Chalmers. About half of the graduates from this double degree program in engineering and education choose to take their first job in schools, while the most of the others pursue careers as engineers in industry.

Their dual qualification raises intriguing questions about career decision-making: what motivates students to enrol in such a hybrid program, and how do they ultimately choose between two distinct professional paths? Zarske, Vadeen and Tsai (2016) found that students studying a similar double degree program in the US identified themselves as both engineers and teachers. Cronhjort (2017) found that student chose a double degree program in engineering and education as they found the combination attractive and because they were unsure of what career to choose.

While studies have explored dual-identity professionals, little is known about how engineering-education students in Sweden navigate their final career decisions. In this study we want to investigate the factors that shape career preferences among students enrolled in the double-degree program at Chalmers in Sweden, who are uniquely positioned at the intersection of two professional identities.

We explore how personal motivations, educational experiences, and social influences interact to guide their career decisions. Both external and intrinsic motivation is considered, especially drawing on Self-Determination Theory where autonomy, mastery, and purpose emerged as key drivers of intrinsic motivation (Deci & Ryan, 2012). By examining the respondent's reflections, we aim to shed light on how career aspirations evolve and what this means for efforts to address the STEM teacher shortage through interdisciplinary education.

We have chosen the following two research questions.

RQ1: At what time did the respondents decide to enrol in a double-degree program in engineering and education, and why?

RQ3: Which internal and external factors shape students' career decisions when entering the job market with degrees in both engineering and education?

Method

Thirteen students in the final stage of the double degree program were interviewed. All participants had completed undergraduate studies in engineering. They were in the final stage of their masters studies eligible for a double degree in engineering and education, leading to teaching certification in upper secondary mathematics and either physics, chemistry, or technology. All 13 students enrolled in the final year of the Learning and Leadership program at Chalmers during the 2024/2025 academic year were invited and agreed to participate.

Semi-structured interviews were conducted by the author (Ruslin et al., 2022). The semi-structured interview guide was designed to align with the study's two research questions and covered three chronological phases: motivations before university, experiences during the program, and anticipated career decisions.

Each interview lasted between 30 and 60 minutes and was audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim. The interview guide was informed by self-determination theory (Deci & Ryan,

2012) and previous work on double-degree programs (Bengmark et al., 2021, Zarske, 2016).

Thematic analysis followed Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase framework: familiarization with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and producing the report. Transcripts were coded inductively, allowing patterns and themes to emerge organically from the data. Coding focused on motivations, perceived barriers and enablers, and social influences. Trustworthiness was enhanced through iterative coding and triangulation with program documentation and prior research on engineering education and teacher recruitment. Informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Results

Some respondents decided to go for the double degree program already when studying at high school. Several of them specifically went to university to be able to get a double degree.

"I found this program already in the second year of high school [...] it was the plan all along." (S4)

Several of these respondents explained their choice by having double interests and that they could delay their choice of career through a double degree program,

"I wasn't 100% sure [...] so teaching was my main goal, but to keep the door open, it sounded great to become both an engineer and a teacher". (S6)

Several participants mentioned being influenced by inspirational teachers or family members. For instance, one respondent was inspired by two female teachers who were also engineers.

"I had two very good high school teachers who were both engineers and teachers. [...] I thought I wanted to become like them." (S4)

In the local region there are other much more broadly known institutions for teacher education. Chalmers is primarily known for engineering education. Still there are early choosers wanting to become teachers that found their way to the double degree program.

"When I was about 17, I decided I wanted to become a teacher. [...] then I found out that you could study Learning and Leadership" (S9)

"I wanted both to study more physics and math and to become a teacher. [...] that was the plan all along." (S4)

There were also respondents who decided to choose the double degree program when they were studying their bachelor at Chalmers. Several of them found an interest in teaching during their bachelor's education.

“I got quite involved in teaching activities during the entire bachelor’s, and I thought that was really, really enjoyable... So that’s kind of the background to why I chose Learning and Leadership later. (S2)

Some of them had been involved in organizations teaching high school students, others just helped their bachelor peers. One respondent describes the culture of peer teaching in their engineering program and the intrinsic satisfaction from those moments as aligning well with a teaching career.

"There is clearly an interest in helping to teach your classmates from the perspective of 'I know this, I can explain it to you' [...] many are really quite good at teaching each other". (S3)

Some refer to the joy in making a difference for others and wanting to make a difference.

“If I can be the teacher I needed [...] then that’s what I want to do.” (S9)

"You can feel greater meaning in school [...] in influencing young people in the right direction". (S1)

“I want to move the world in a positive direction?” (S13)

Some students saw the double degree as a way to keep doors open. They noted the appeal of flexibility—being able to work either in industry or education. It would give economic security and versatility in career options in an uncertain job market.

“It’s also nice to have both paths [...] it makes me feel more secure.” (S3)

“I won’t be unemployed [...] that’s what’s great about my education.” (S8)

Now let us turn our focus to the responses pertaining to the second research question. In the end of their studies, what makes them choose job sector?

Many students highlights that the school-based teaching practicum was formative and sometimes a decisive factor. Some students found that the classroom environment energizes them, confirming their interest in teaching or made them they realize they prefer other forms of education or the structure of industry.

“The practicum was character-defining in a way.” (S4)

“I don’t want this practicum to end.” (S9)

“I’ve done a lot of training [...] but within industry. That appeals to me more.” (S1)

Students sometimes weigh external validation in their final decision. Some feel teaching lacks prestige and must defend the choice to sceptical peers or family, while others feel affirmed in that direction. Students reported feeling the need to justify their career choices, especially when leaning toward teaching.

“A bit like you’re throwing your education away [...] that’s the general attitude.” (S4)

“They said to me: are you going to be a teacher? [...] I said: you can become both a teacher and an engineer.” (S8)

Finally, several students stated that they plan to start their careers in engineering, not because they see it as their destination, but because they believe it will be easier to transition from engineering to teaching than the other way around.

“It feels easier to go into engineering and fall back on teaching, rather than start in teaching and then try to find my way back into engineering.” (S6)

None of the respondents thought that salaries had an influential part in their decision, referring to that the starting salaries for engineers and teachers in Sweden are comparable even if they can differ considerably later in the career.

Discussion

Some students identified their dual interests early, choosing the university specifically for the double-degree opportunity. This early commitment often stemmed from double interests and a desire to keep career options open, aligning with the findings of Zarske et al. (2016). Others discovered an interest in education during their bachelor's studies, often through teaching-related extra-curricular or peer-support experiences. Both early and late commitment to studying a double degree program aligns with the Chalmers initiative as described by Bengmark, Lundh, and Gerlee (2021),

The students' final career decisions were shaped by both internal motivations and external validations. Practicum experiences were often transformative, providing emotional resonance and practical insights that clarified professional identities. Those leaning toward the teaching profession described a strong sense of agency, purpose, and societal contribution, echoing the concepts of autonomy and meaningfulness from self-determination theory (Deci & Ryan, 2012). Others, however, found greater alignment with the structured, perhaps more predictable environment of engineering work.

Societal perceptions also emerged as critical external influences. Several students noted that teaching, though personally rewarding, is seen as less prestigious than engineering, a view sometimes expressed by peers and family. These perceptions sometimes necessitated justification of their choices, especially when diverging from the expected engineering track, an issue also noted in the Education and Training Monitor (European Commission, 2023) which highlights societal undervaluation of teaching in STEM fields. Interestingly, many students expressed the intention to start in industry and potentially transition to education later. This strategy was seen as both a practical response to labor market dynamics and a way to preserve long-term flexibility.

Notably, salary considerations were not a significant factor for most participants. This contrasts with common assumptions about economic incentives in career choice but aligns with Kahneman and Deaton's (2010) finding that income beyond a certain threshold does not strongly affect life satisfaction. In the Swedish context, respondents viewed both careers as viable in terms of financial stability.

Implications for education

By sharing the experiences, we hope to encourage other universities to address the STEM teacher shortage by offering similar double-degree programs in engineering and education. This study offers insight into aspects that are valuable to consider when designing and running such a program.

For example, it highlights the role of early exposure to teaching, through tutoring, mentoring, or school-based experiences, as a recurring factor in shaping participants' interest in education. Integrating structured opportunities for teaching practice earlier in engineering curricula may help identify and support students with latent interest in teaching. Furthermore, the practicum was a pivotal experience for many students, often confirming or reshaping their career aspirations. This underscores the importance of ensuring high-quality practicum placements.

The double-degree students appreciated the flexibility and job security. Programs should recognize and support this hybridity to make students find a career path that suits them also if it means moving between the sectors over time. By acknowledging and responding to these insights, institutions can better support students at the intersection of engineering and education—and potentially help alleviate the chronic shortage of STEM teachers through more purposeful recruitment and retention strategies.

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